

PROPERTIES AND THERMOSTRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FELT-CARBON COMPOSITES AT ULTRA-HIGH TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the thermophysical properties, tensile and compressive properties of carbon felt-carbon at ultra-high temperature are systematically measured, the complete data of the properties are obtained. The average thermal expansion coefficients from room temperature to 1273K, the thermal conductivity and specific heat from room temperature to 2573K are given. Based on the technique of rapid resistive self-heating, the ultimate strength in tension and compression are reported as a function of temperature up to 3073K. The mechanism that carbon felt-carbon composites have the specific properties at ultra-high temperature is discussed. Based on the testing results of the physical and mechanical properties, thermal stress resistance (TSR) which is the most important parameter for this kind of materials is analyzed. According to the results obtained above and taking into account the changes of the properties of composites with temperature, the transient temperature and stress fields of the throat are analyzed.

KEY WORDS: carbon felt-carbon composites, properties at ultra-high temperature, thermostructural behavior

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-Carbon composites have found only limited commercial use owing to their relatively high cost of manufacture, but are essential and irreplaceable in several instances. Examples are brakes for supersonic aircraft and components in solid-fuel rocket nozzles. Because C/C material is expensive and not a simple off-the-shelf material, the type and structure of the composite which is best suited for any given application must be considered. In order to make the correct choice of the commercial product best suited for the application, the designer must get key property data for a structure analysis.

Carbon felt-carbon composites are successfully used in the areas of aeronautics, astronautics and national defence since they have a series of advantages which can not be substituted. Usually, this kind of materials is applied in the environments with transient and ultra-high temperature and has the complexity of properties and thermostructural behavior, so it is important and valuable in both application and academic field to investigate carbon felt-carbon composites. However, the lack of accurate or reliable physical and mechanical properties for composite materials at correlated temperature, often results in a bad correlation

between calculated and measured mechanical behavior.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

The Carbon felt-carbon composite materials used in this study was manufactured by Shanxi Institute of Nonmetal Materials. A Carbon felt was derived from the pyrolysis of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibers, and the structure was manufactured through Integrated needling procedures. Test specimens were machined from the as-deposited and heat-treated component. Test directions are specified since the composite properties are not truly isotropic. This is due to the carding and subsequent needling procedures during felting which tend to align fibers preferentially within the inplane of the felt (1-Direction) and few perpendicular to it (2-Direction). The two directions within the plane were considered to be equivalent.

MECHANICAL TESTING OF CARBON FELT-CARBON MATERIALS AT ULTRA-HIGH TEMPERATURE

A experimental method based on rapid resistive self-heating of the specimen, with automatic control of the heating, loading and data acquisition, is developed to measure the mechanical properties of Carbon-Carbon materials at up to 2800°C. We gained our ends through improving Gleeble 1500. shown in Fig.1. The sample is suspended between one fixed and one movable electrode and heated in the vacuum of more than 5×10^{-4} torr. The software used in conjunction with the computer-based digital data acquisition system controls parts of the experiments, collects all the data, and computes and outputs results. The automatic control of the heating is realized by using the Pulsar-II 1700 photoelectric pyrometer with an appropriate apertures and CIT-1 infrared pyrometer with an effective wavelength of 1.06 μm , and temperature profiles are determined on the sample by thermo-video system[1-3]. High temperature strengths and moduli were measured by unidirectional tensile and compression testing. The specimens of tensile were dumb-bell shape, 10mm in effective diameter and 25mm in effective length; the specimens of compression were cylinders, 8mm in diameter and 12mm in length. There were 5 ~ 7 samples in each testing point.

Fig.1: Schematic diagram of testing equipment

Each sample was tested to failure and moduli were obtained from the initial slopes of the load-deflection curves. The ultimate strength, the initial elastic modulus and strain-to-failure in tension and compression which are important for the design and strength analysis of C/C components could be obtained. The ultimate strength of carbon felt - carbon materials in tension and compression are reported as a function of temperature up to 3073K (shown in Fig.1 and Fig.2). One of the major assets of a carbon-carbon composite is that of retention of mechanical properties at high temperatures. In all cases the strength and modulus rise with the temperature up to 2200K~2400K, then descend as result of the one set of plastic deformation of carbon.

Fig.2: Tensile strengths of carbon felt-carbon composites at high temperature

Fig.3: Compressive strengths of carbon felt-carbon composites at high temperature

Great care must be taken to avoid failure in the transition region between the hot and cold zone.

THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FELT-CARBON MATERIALS

Measurement of thermal expansion

Thermal expansion is an important property when using materials at high temperatures. Linear thermal expansions of carbon felt - carbon composites were measured to 1400K on Brinkman dilatometers which used sapphire push-rods and which were calibrated against a platinum standard. The samples were cylinders, 4mm in diameter and 25mm in length. The average thermal expansion coefficients from room temperature to 1273K were given in Fig.4. There were differences in 1-Direction and 2-Direction, but few changes with temperature rising.

Fig.4: Average thermal expansion parameters of carbon felt-carbon composites

Measurement of thermal conductivity

Thermal diffusivities were measured by the laser flash technique to 2400K in different directions on discs 10mm in diameter and 4mm in thick. The thermal conductivity K, was calculated from the diffusivity by the relation:

$$K = D C_p \rho \quad (1)$$

where D is the measured diffusivity, C_p is the specific heat, and ρ is the measured bulk density of the test specimen[4]. Fig.5 and Fig.6 show the relationship between measurement temperature and the thermal conductivity of the carbon felt-carbon materials in 1-Direction and 2-Direction from room temperature to 2573K. As the temperature is increased, the thermal conductivity descends and trends to steady.

THERMAL STRESS RESISTANCE

The improvement of thermal stress resistance has been a continued goal of Carbon-Carbon composite development and is particularly important in carbon felt composites which exhibit a characteristic brittle fracture. One measure of thermal stress resistance is expressed by the relation[5]:

$$TSR = (\sigma / K) (\alpha) = (\text{strength}) / (\text{thermal conductivity}) (\text{modulus}) (\text{thermal expansion}) \quad (2)$$

Fig.5: The relationship of thermal conductivity for carbon felt-carbon composites and temperature (1-Direction)

Fig.6: The relationship of thermal conductivity for carbon felt-carbon composites and temperature (2-Direction)

This thermal stress parameter is not exact for materials in the environments with transient and ultra-high temperature, but it does provide a useful method for qualitatively ranking the thermal stress resistance of various materials. Based on the testing results of the physical and mechanical properties, thermal stress resistance (TSR) which is a important parameter for this kind of materials is analyzed and given in Fig.7. The large uncertainties in the individual properties do not allow meaningful uncertainties to be assigned to the TSRs. The results show that there are different parameters between in 1-Direction and 2-Direction.

Fig.7: Thermal stress resistance parameters of carbon felt-carbon composites at high temperature

THERMOSTRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Key properties of Carbon-Carbon, such as good strength retention at temperatures approaching 3000K, low density, dimensional stability and complex shape fabricability, make carbon-carbon materials an appropriate materials for a variety of evolving applications. A difficulty truly exists because the constitutes that one starts with are modified by the high temperatures during processing and application.

Analysis techniques have rapidly evolved within recent years, owing to the development of large and sophisticated computer programs. Analytical tools are now available to accurately predict the stress filed induced in complex structures such as multi-dimension Carbon-Carbon structures subjected to a severe mechanical and thermochemical environment. FEM program, such as NASTRAN, PATRAN, ANYSIS and some programs that we researched, can obtained the strain and stress fields of a complicated C/C composites structure.

Since the throat of Solid Rocket Motor (SRM) is the most typical structure of carbon felt-carbon composites which are applied in the extreme condition such as high temperature, high press and so on, its thermostructural behavior is studied in this paper. According to the test results obtained above and taking into account the changes of the properties of composites with temperature, the transient temperature and stress fields of the throat are analyzed. The finite element model of carbon felt - carbon throat is shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8: The finite element model of carbon felt- carbon throat

Fig.9: Effect of properties of composites as a function of temperature on stress S_{11} of the Section 1

In the Fig.9, real lines represent the stresses without considering changes of the properties of carbon felt- carbon composites with temperature, and broken lines are the results considering these changes. It can be found that the variations of the thermophysical and mechanical properties of carbon felt-carbon composites with temperature have the obvious effects on the stress fields of the thermostructure under the transient high temperature. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the changes of the properties of composites with temperature, especially at ultra-high temperature.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Carbon felt, carbon matrix composites have the similar high-temperature mechanical properties as other carbon-carbon composites. According to the electrical conductivity of Carbon, the technique of rapid resistive self-heating is an effective and economical method to measure the properties of carbon-carbon materials. We realized this technique by improving Gleeble 1500. But there are a lot of parts need to be improved such as environment cabin, high-temperature collect and so on.

Studied on the microstructure, the mechanical and physical properties of Carbon-carbon composites and thermostructure analysis of C/C parts at high temperature are of considerable importance since these composites are applied in the critical area. Solving this problem will push modern astronautic technology forward to higher reliability. It is hoped that this information will open up new applications where high temperature, corrosion and erosion, and high stresses are involved, and where light weight is of advantage.

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